
**A STUDY OF ENVIRONMENT AWARENESS AMONG PASS-OUT STUDENTS IN B.A. AND
B.COM. PART-II AT ARTS AND COMMERCE COLLEGE, NAGTHANE DIST SATARA
(MAHARASHTRA)**

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INTRODUCTION

The environmental education is the study of nature, natural resources, the interrelationship with man, human activities, disturbances of the environment and the attempts to improve the environment. It is an application of knowledge from different disciplines to study and manage the environment. It is also study of the conditions, circumstances and influences that affect life and how life in turn responds. Life requires the correct balance of environment condition to survive. Environmental study is based upon a comprehensive views of various environmental systems. It aims to make the citizens competent to do scientific work and to find out practical solution to current environmental problem.

This study finds out the awareness and implementation of environmental education in society through graduate students.

IMPORTANCE OF STUDY

Environment is main base of human growth and living life. Human being is direct and indirect depending on a environment because environment plays vital role in every activity of human. Hence the environmental education is a need to young generation of India. The University Grant Commission has formed a committee of expert on environmental studies. This was followed by framing of the core module syllabus of environmental studies for all undergraduate courses. The University Grant Commission has made it compulsory to all universities and colleges in India as per the directives of the Hon'ble Supreme Court of India.

Hon'ble vice-chancellor has endorsed the scheme to the Dean of social science faculty for designing the course curricula. According it has been studied thoroughly and the scheme of it's implementation has been prepared and forwarded to the college.

The course vision is the importance of environmental studies cannot be disputed. The need of sustainable development is a key to the future of mankind, continuing the problem of pollution, loss of forest, solid waste disposal, degradation of environment, issues like economic productivity and national security, global warming, the depletion of ozone layer and loss of biodiversity have made everyone aware of environmental issues. The united nation conference on world summit on sustainable development at Johannesburg in 2002 have draw the attention of people around the globe to the deteriorating condition of our environment. It is clear that no citizen of the earth can afford to be ignorant of environmental issues. Environmental management has captured the attention of health can managers, managing environmental hazards has become very important. For the development of environment awareness among student.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Assessment of environmental awareness among students in graduate level in colleges.

OBJECTIVES

- To find the level of attendance and participation in extension activities of student in class and college.
- To find the level of environmental awareness of students after completion degree course.
- To study the level of environmental awareness of the students after degree course in college and its dimension.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Data Collection:

Data are collected through questionnaire in sample college Arts and Commerce college, Nagthane Tal & Dist : Satara.(Maharashtra)

2. Research Methodology:

The present study adopted 'survey method' and sampling technique to collect data. The pass out student forms the population for the study. The sample is 150. The investigator has planned to take of around 80 percent of the population about the sample.

The investigator perused the tools available in the market. Since there is no standard tool available for assessing the environmental awareness. The investigators worked out strategy to prepare and validate his own research tools studying the environmental awareness. To establish item validity of the tool, a pilot study was done. The data collected were statistically analyzed and conclusions were drawn. For establishing the validity for the prepared draft tool the investigator made use of content validity and item validity.

DELIMITATIONS:

The study is restricted to only 150 pass out students from single college in Nagthane Tal & Dist. Satara (Maharashtra) area, with limited variables and dimensions.

STRATIFICATION:

The data has been collected randomly based on the stratification given below.

ANALYSIS

Environment is an important factor of human life. Day by day population increases and environment decreases. In 21st century awareness and environmental education are must to living life of human. Then some educational institute, government and NGO'S are trying to providing the best knowledge of environment and there conservation. But is this knowledge really going to every human? Are students

getting this knowledge? Are students applying the rules are environmental awareness? These questions are arising today hence present study and analysis trying to solve and answer of these questions.

Following tables are describing the level of environmental awareness.

Dimensions	N	Low		Average		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Pollution	150	48	32.00	67	44.60	35	23.33
Biodiversity	150	55	36.60	45	30.00	50	33.33
Natural Resources	150	41	27.33	49	32.60	60	40.00
Energy Resources	150	67	44.60	43	28.60	40	26.60
Sustainable Development	150	83	55.30	38	25.30	29	19.30
Environmental Conservation	150	38	25.30	41	27.30	71	47.33
Population	150	30	20.00	40	26.60	80	53.33
Total	150	32	21.33	83	55.30	35	23.33

The level of environmental awareness of students in Arts and Commerce College, Nagthane and its dimension is average. Only awareness about natural resources, Environmental Conservation and Population are high percentage in pass out students. Most important is awareness about Pollution, Biodiversity, Energy Resources and Sustainable Development are low percentage in pass out student.

Variable	N	Average		High	
		N	%	N	%
Extension Activities	150	88	58.67	62	41.33

The level of participation in extension activities of pass out student in Arts and Commerce College, Nagthane in Satara district is average.

Dimensions	Male				Female			
	N	Percentage			N	Percentage		
		Low	Average	High		Low	Average	High
Pollution	50	45	37	18	100	20	58	22
Biodiversity	50	21	49	30	100	24	33	43
Natural Resources	50	53	32	15	100	36	49	15
Energy Resources	50	55	29	16	100	22	46	32
Sustainable Development	50	61	31	08	100	49	27	24
Environmental Conservation	50	38	40	22	100	32	39	29
Population	50	25	32	43	100	13	31	56
Total /Average	50	42.57	35.71	21.71	100	28.00	40.42	31.57

The level of environmental awareness of pass out students in Arts and Commerce College, Nagthane in Satara districts with regards to their female student average, but level of environmental awareness in male students is low.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. Most important is environmental education is included in a main syllabus or there is need to increase its value like other regular subject.
2. Seminar, workshop, booster programs and interactive programs organizing may be conduct about environmental awareness of the students.
3. Camps activity like cleaning, plantation trees, making awareness to urban, rural and illiterate people through students will increase aptitude and attitude towards environment.
4. World earth day, world population day, world wild life day, world ozone day may be conducted in student.
5. Government are included the college student for various activity of forest and animal conservation camps.

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